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Modeling the relationship between information literacy with creativity and Entrepreneurial capabilities of Physical Education Graduated students of Tehran Universities

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was modeling the relationship between information literacy with creativity and entrepreneurial capabilities of Physical Education Graduated students of Tehran Universities. The Statistical population were all of the Physical Education graduated students of Tehran Universities (N=1000). According to Morgan table sample, 270 people were chosen with sampling stratified random method. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used for modeling. The results showed that information literacy has a direct impact upon entrepreneurial capabilities and creativity with path coefficient (pc) of 0.19 and 0.44, respectively. “The Ability to access information”, “The ability to use targeted information”, “The ability to understand the legal and economic information”, “The ability to critically evaluate information” and “The ability to understand the extent and nature of the information” played the most important roles with impact factors of 0.81, 0.76, 0.33, 0.31 and 0.16, respectively. Also, creativity had a direct impact on entrepreneurial capabilities with path coefficient of 0.28. Regarding to this results, in order to develop entrepreneurial capabilities as well as creativity of physical education students, it is necessary to put on appropriate educational content and effective education related to improving information literacy in the curriculum of physical education students.

Keywords: Physical Education, Creativity, Student, Information literacy, Entrepreneurship

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